

The development of science and culture in Uzbekistan during the years of independence

Shamsiyeva Narzigul Olimovna

Master of Science, Asian University of Technology

+998 91 815 64 14

Abstract. This article analyzes the reforms, achievements, and future plans in the fields of science and culture in Uzbekistan during the years of independence. It discusses the development of research institutions, innovation, the revival of national culture, international cooperation, digital culture, and youth policy.

Keywords: science, culture, independence, innovation, digital culture, cultural heritage, youth policy, international cooperation, reforms, national values.

During the years of independence, one of the most important areas of Uzbekistan's development was the fields of science and culture. Science and culture are the spiritual foundation of every nation. After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained state independence in 1991, it began to independently form its scientific and cultural policy. Special attention was paid to the development of these areas in our country. In particular, the activities of scientific institutions and higher education institutions were reviewed. An inextricable link was created between science and education. Attention was increased to the introduction of new technologies. Attention was increased in the field of culture to national heritage. Holy places and historical monuments were restored. The activities of cultural centers, theaters and museums were expanded. Uzbek art entered the international stage. The scope of scientific research expanded. State grants began to be allocated for innovative projects. Digital technologies entered the fields of science and culture. The state has developed strategic programs in the formation of science policy. A system of support for young scientists and creative people has been established. International scientific and cultural ties have been strengthened. The foundations of an educated, intellectual society are being created in Uzbekistan. On this basis, this article will provide a comprehensive analysis of the development of science and culture during the years of independence.

During the years of independence, special attention was paid to science and culture in Uzbekistan at the state level. Many laws, decrees and programs were adopted to develop scientific potential. In particular, the law "On the Development of Scientific and Innovative Activities" served to modernize the scientific system. The activities of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan were radically reformed. The number and quality of scientific research related to higher education were increased. In 2020, the "Fund for Support of Scientific Research Activities" was established.¹ This fund serves to encourage young scientists.

The number of innovative projects and startups in science has increased. Scientific ideas are being commercialized on the basis of the principle of "New Uzbekistan is a place of innovation". Technoparks have been established at many higher educational institutions. They are creating laboratories and incubation environments for young researchers. In addition, through participation in international projects, Uzbek scientists have begun to enter the global scientific arena. In the field of culture, one of the most important achievements has been the restoration and strengthening of national

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi rasmiy sayti – www.academy.uz

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identity. From the first years of independence, the Uzbek language received state status and began to be actively used in official documents, scientific publications and the media. A number of historical holidays have been restored - such as Navruz, Independence Day, Constitution Day. The “Cultural Heritage Agency” has been established under the Ministry of Culture. This agency is cataloging, restoring and digitizing thousands of historical works.

Many creative festivals have been organized in theater, music, literature, and folk arts. Uzbek artists are recognized by UNESCO. The development of national media and the film industry, such as “Uzbekkino”, “Uzbekfilm”, and “UzReport TV”, has also enriched the cultural climate. Along with the development of the Internet and digital platforms, cultural content has also diversified. The “Culture and Enlightenment” TV channel, electronic libraries, digital museums, and archives are being created. International cooperation plays a crucial role in the development of science and culture. Uzbekistan has established cooperation with many international organizations - UNESCO, ISESCO, COMSTECH, and the European Science Foundation. Joint conferences, grants, and exchange programs on culture and science have been organized. This allows Uzbekistan to demonstrate its scientific and cultural potential to the world.

Within the framework of youth policy, structures such as the “Creation” Foundation and the “Youth Academy” have been established, and support for talented young people has been strengthened. Presidential scholarships, international olympiads, grants and scholarships have increased interest in the field of science and culture. In general, science and culture are becoming one of the pillars of the modernization and development of Uzbekistan.

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, the development of science and culture was identified as one of the main priorities of the country's development. Reforms in this area began from the first days of independence and became the main principle of state policy. In order to ensure scientific and cultural independence, fundamental systemic changes were implemented. The Academy of Sciences was revised and its activities were modernized based on the requirements of the time. Research institutes were reorganized, their specialization and scientific potential were strengthened. Cooperation between higher education institutions and scientific institutions was strengthened, as a result of which innovative solutions were put into practice. New approaches to financing science were developed, and competitive projects were encouraged through scientific grants and competitions.

Special programs have been developed for young scientists, and the system of training scientific personnel has been improved. Doctoral and postdoctoral programs have been expanded, and modern technoparks have been established. This has contributed to the implementation of scientific developments in production. Scientific and technical strategies have been developed, and digital technologies are being actively applied in research. Online libraries and open databases are being created, and scientific articles are being published on international platforms. A system for assessing and monitoring scientific activity has been established. As a result, Uzbek scientists are finding their place in international rankings, and the number of joint projects with foreign centers is increasing. Science is becoming the driving force of the country's economic development, and scientific potential is becoming crucial in the process of transition to an innovative economy.

In the field of culture, the process of national revival began during the years of independence, and the preservation and study of historical heritage became an important direction of state policy. Museums, theaters, palaces of culture and art schools were modernized, Uzbek national art - music, literature, dance and applied arts - actively developed. Many historical monuments were restored,

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some of them were included in the UNESCO list. Separate state programs to support culture were adopted, the activities of non-governmental organizations expanded. Art festivals, exhibitions, competitions were regularly held, and opportunities were created for young talents. Uzbek artists are receiving international awards, and Uzbekkino and other studios are actively participating in the production of national content.

Through digital cultural media, the general public is getting acquainted with cultural values, electronic libraries and archives are being created, and cultural and spiritual TV channels are serving the intellectual and spiritual awakening of citizens. The cultural sphere is also actively integrating internationally - through international forums, art exhibitions, and scientific expeditions, the culture of Uzbekistan is being represented on the world stage. At the same time, the cultural potential in the tourism sector is being effectively used.

Science and culture are mutually complementary strategic directions, and their integration plays a major role in shaping social consciousness, developing national pride and intellectual potential. A stable approach to these two areas has been formed in state policy, which is reinforced by strategic programs and an improving legal framework. Civil society institutions are also actively participating in this process, as a result of which the scientific and cultural environment is improving. The development of these areas ensures not only spiritual, but also economic stability.

In conclusion, during the years of independence, Uzbekistan has managed to form an intellectual society and create a solid foundation for economic and political development through the consistent development of science and culture. Achievements in this area serve as a foundation for future generations. Today, Uzbekistan is increasingly strengthening its position in the world community with its scientific and cultural potential.

The following proposals are aimed at ensuring a more sustainable and effective development of the spheres of science and culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan, each of which is based on the current scientific basis and modern trends. First of all, it is necessary to further increase the budget allocated to scientific research. In today's era of globalization, the competitiveness of countries largely depends on their scientific and innovative potential. The quality of scientific research, the level of training of scientific personnel, and the ability to create innovative products directly depend on the volume of financial resources directed to science. The experience of developed countries (for example, South Korea, Germany, the USA) shows that allocating at least 2 percent of GDP to scientific research is an important factor in achieving high technological achievements and ensuring economic growth. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, too, the budget allocated to science should be gradually increased.

It is also important to increase joint scientific programs with domestic and foreign higher education institutions. Expanding scientific cooperation is of great importance in increasing the potential of science through international exchange of experience, transfer of advanced technologies, and joint projects. In particular, research conducted jointly with prestigious foreign universities serves to increase the number of articles published in international scientific journals, develop innovative products, and increase the socio-economic impact of scientific activities. Such programs open the way for young scientists to receive international internships, joint dissertation defenses, and grants.

In addition, there is a need to expand the digital cultural infrastructure in the regions. When the cultural sphere is combined with digital technologies, its scope of influence and the effectiveness of its delivery to the public increase. Although digital cultural centers are currently operating in the capital and large cities, this direction is poorly developed in the regions and remote areas. This violates the principle of equal opportunities for culture. Therefore, by establishing digital libraries,

virtual museums, and online art education platforms in the regions, cultural knowledge and values will be delivered to all strata of society. This process will increase the level of cultural literacy, creative activity, and spiritual education.

It is also relevant to develop online platforms to promote cultural heritage internationally. Uzbekistan has a rich historical and cultural heritage, and it is of strategic importance to widely introduce this heritage to the world community. Modern digital technologies create broad opportunities in this regard. In particular, through virtual exhibitions, 3D-modeled historical monuments, multilingual interactive websites, it is possible to bring cultural monuments and examples of national art to a global audience. Such platforms serve as a means of cultural diplomacy, contribute to the development of tourism and strengthening the international image of the country. Therefore, it is necessary to form complex information systems based on modern and digital communication technologies with state support in this area.

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